

MAGNETIC SEMICONDUCTORS AND SPINTRONICS

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Annotation: One of the main tasks of spintronics is the integration of magnetic systems into semiconductor microelectronics. The easy control of electron spins in semiconductors today allows the creation of two new classes of hybrid materials: magnetic semiconductors (ferromagnetic/semiconductor hybrid structure) and spin-electron nanotransistors.

Broad prospects for the application of nanoheterostructures are related to the fact that the electronic spins of a semiconductor can be used as detectors that respond to changes in the magnetic state in a ferromagnet. Thus, when injected through the contact of a ferromagnet and a semiconductor, the electrons of the semiconductor will have an unbalanced spin that contains information about the spin of the electrons in the ferromagnet. Both optical and electrical detection methods can be used to determine the spin direction of electrons in a semiconductor.

Key words: magnetic semiconductors, spin-electron nanotransistors, ferromagnetic, semiconductor, spin injectors

Аннотация: Одной из основных задач спинтроники является интеграция магнитных систем в полупроводниковую микроэлектронику. Легкое управление спинами электронов в полупроводниках сегодня позволяет создать два новых класса гибридных материалов: магнитные полупроводники (гибридная структура ферромагнетик/полупроводник) и спин-электронные нанотранзисторы.

Широкие перспективы применения наногетероструктур связаны с тем, что электронные спины полупроводника могут быть использованы в качестве детекторов, реагирующих на изменение магнитного состояния в ферромагнетике. Таким образом, при инжекции через контакт ферромагнетика и полупроводника электроны полупроводника будут иметь несбалансированный спин, содержащий информацию о спине электронов в ферромагнетике. Для определения направления вращения электронов в полупроводнике можно использовать как оптические, так и электрические методы обнаружения.

Ключевые слова: магнитные полупроводники, спин-электронные нанотранзисторы, ферромагнетики, полупроводники, спиновые инжекторы.

INTRODUCTION

However, according to many scientists and experts, in the next few decades, without conceptual solutions, microelectronics will drastically reduce the pace of development.⁴

In the 21st century, one of the promising directions of the development of microelectronics is semiconductor spintronics, which uses the charge of the electron as well as its spin (internal angular momentum). Semiconductor spintronics opens up the possibility of creating basic elements that expand the functionality of existing devices, and also allows the production of electronic devices based on new effects and phenomena in principle (magnetoresistive memory; quantum computer; spin transistors, valves, magnetic sensors). Spintronic devices are fast and energy efficient because the spin of an electron can be transferred from one state to another in less time than the transfer of energy and charge.

Since the kinetic energy of the charge carrier does not change when the spin changes, practically no heat is released

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Magnetic semiconductors. All spintronic devices described above have in common that they are based on metal. An important disadvantage of this approach is the inability to amplify signals. There are no exact metal analogues of traditional semiconductor transistors today, in which the flow of electrons from the base of the transistor allows dozens of others to flow from the emitter to the collector. Finding materials with ferromagnetic and semiconductor properties has been a long-standing dream of researchers. But this is difficult to achieve, because there is a great difference in the nature of chemical bonds. Ferromagnetic semiconductors, on the one hand, are sources of spin-polarized electrons, and on the other hand, they are easily integrated with conventional semiconductor devices. *The band structure of a magnetic semiconductor* differs from the two-band structure of conventional semiconductors, metals and dielectrics by the presence of a special third band formed by *d-* and *f-electrons* of transition atoms or rare earth elements. Ideal ferromagnetic semiconductor The conductor should have a Curie temperature above room

⁴ MoS₂ transistors with 1-nanometer gate lengths / SB Desai, SR Madhvapathy, AB Sachid et al. // Science. - 2016. - Vol. 354, No. 6308. - P. 99-102.

temperature (the temperature at which a ferromagnet loses its properties) *and should allow the formation of*⁵*n-* and *p-* conduction bands in the crystal .

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Today, much attention is being paid to the so-called alloys (GaAs), in which individual atoms are replaced by atoms with random magnetic properties, such as dilute magnetic semiconductors containing Mn^{2+} . The highest Curie temperature $T_c = 110 K$ has been achieved so far in GaMnAs magnetic solid solution with *p* - conductivity . This material was used as a spin injector (including zero external magnetic field) in an electroluminescent diode with a non-magnetic InGaAs/GaAs quantum well.⁶

Currently, the search for new ferromagnetic semiconductors with a high Curie temperature, which can be used as spin injectors at temperatures of the order of room temperature and in a weak (or zero) external magnetic field, is in full swing. The most interesting results in this direction are given in which ferromagnetism is observed at $T_c = 320 K$ in a semiconductor with $CdMn_{1-x}Ge_xP_2$ chalcopyrite structure .

Figure 1. (a) Schematic of a Johnson spin transistor, (b) Schematic of a spin-valve transistor

Johnson spin transistor . The development of microelectronics facilitated a rapid transition from two-contact spin-electronic devices to three-contact systems

⁵ El-Aawar H. Increasing the transistor count by constructing a two-layer crystal square on a single chip / Intern. journal of comp. science & information. tech. - 2015. - Vol. 7, No. 3. - P. 97-105.

⁶ Borisov E. Spintronics. Kuda dvigatsya dalshe? / E. Borisov // Vector high-tech. - 2013. - T. 4, No. 4. - S. 41-45.

consisting of two ferromagnetic layers separated by a paramagnetic layer and exhibiting a large magnetoresistance effect. Such a device was called a Johnson transistor in honor of the inventor who connected the third contact to the paramagnetic layer. Speaking of bipolar transistors, a Johnson transistor consists of a base (paramagnetic), an emitter and a collector (ferromagnet). If a potential is applied to the collector, electrons in the up/down direction are collected in the emitter-base circuit. The collector current now depends on whether its magnetic moment is parallel or antiparallel to the emitter magnetization. The ferromagnetic emitter in this case plays the role of a polarizer for the collected spins. It is clear that to change the potential in the circuit of the emitter-base, it is necessary to apply an external magnetic field, which "changes" the magnetic moment vector of the collector or emitter in the opposite direction.⁷

Hybrid spintronics . The Johnson transistor is very functional, but it still has limitations in its use. The measured voltage values are very small and cannot be increased without the use of additional devices. The main disadvantage of such structures is that all connections between layers are ohmic, since all components of the structure are metal. *In other words, the researchers* faced the problem of creating a new class of structures - hybrid spin-electronic devices. Such devices represent the combination of magnetic materials with semiconductors. Ferromagnets polarize spins and semiconductors allow voltage blocking, current spreading and tunneling effects.

Single transistor . The first hybrid spin-electronic device was the Monsma transistor, which was a spin valve sandwiched between layers of silicon. Two contacts are connected to the silicon layers (emitter and collector), and the third is connected to the rotary valve (base) (Fig. 5. 4). The spin valve in this structure can be composed of magnetic and non-magnetic metal layers that are repeated over and over again. At the interfaces between silicon and metal , Schottky barriers are formed that absorb bias voltages applied between pairs of contacts (Fig. 5. 5). The collector Schottky barrier is reverse biased, while the emitter barrier is forward biased. This allows unpolarized "hot" electrons from the semiconductor emitter to be sent to the metal base with energies higher than the Fermi energy. The question is: can hot electrons pass through the spin valve and retain enough energy to overcome the Schottky barrier of the collector? Otherwise, they remain in the base and go to the outer circuit. By changing the magnetic configuration of the base, you can determine how much energy the "hot" electrons lose as they pass through the base. If the

⁷ Danilov Yu. A. Magnetic semiconductor nanostructures for spintronic devices / Yu. A. Danilov // Prilozhenie k journal "Vestnik RGRTU". - 2009. - No. 4. - S. 1-6.

magnetic moments of adjacent spin valve layers are antiferromagnetically aligned, then both types of spin are equally distributed in the magnetic layers. If an external magnetic field is applied to the spin valve, which equalizes all the magnetic moments of the layers, then one type of spin (spin down or "minor") is strongly propagated, while the other (spin or "major") passes through the entire magnetic structure without propagation .

(a) (b)

Figure 2. (a) Working principle of SFET, (b) schematic diagram (top) and energy diagram (bottom) of the spin blocking device .

Datta-Das spin field effect transistor (SFET). In 1990, Supriyo Datta and Biswajit Das considered the possibility of creating a spin field effect transistor based on the relativistic effect. The device has a design similar to a conventional field-effect transistor with source and drain contacts (ferromagnets) and a gate (semiconductor). Spin-polarized carriers leave the source with spins and precession parallel to the

magnetization of the ferromagnet when moving due to the Rashba effect (Fig. 2). In this case, electrons must move at a speed of 1% of the speed of light in a vacuum. With sufficient magnetic field strength (in this case, the speed of the electron is very important), the electron spins reverse direction. As a result, the channel resistance increases and the current decreases. By changing the gate potential, the conductance of the device can be changed. This device works like a traditional field-effect transistor, its peculiarity is that the differential magnetization of the contacts (and therefore its electrical properties) is sensitive to the external magnetic field.

New effects in spintronics: spin blockade . At the end of the last century, a new effect was found in the device, the diagram of which is shown in Fig. 2. The spin blocking system consists of cobalt contacts, between which are ferromagnetic cobalt islands, which change the direction of magnetization under the influence of an external magnetic field. For example, Figure 2 shows a Schottky barrier at low temperature, which blocks circuits in such a device. The magnitude of the magnetoresistive effect remains 25% at $T = 20$ K, which is unprecedented for silicon-based devices. The network structure consists of a Schottky barrier, along the edges of which there are a number of magnetic islands, between which an antiferromagnetic coupling is established (and therefore, in the absence of an external magnetic field, o ‘blocks tooth spins).

In a magnetic field, the magnetization vectors of the islands are directed across the field , and the resistance of the structure decreases due to tunneling between adjacent islands. Exposure to optical radiation increases the resistance of the structure, as photons activate the electrons of the islands, resulting in an increase in the density of energy states. The geometry of such a system is not much different from a high electron mobility transistor, in which the conductance of the main current channel is controlled by localized states in adjacent but physically separated regions of the device.

References:

1. MoS₂ transistors with 1-nanometer gate lengths / SB Desai, SR Madhvapathy, AB Sachid et al. // Science. - 2016. - Vol. 354, No. 6308. - P. 99-102.
2. El-Aawar H. Increasing the transistor count by constructing a two-layer crystal square on a single chip / Intern. journal of comp. science & information. tech. - 2015. - Vol. 7, No. 3. - P. 97-105.
3. Borisov E. Spintronics. Kuda dvigatsya dalshe? / E. Borisov // Vector high-tech. - 2013. - T. 4, No. 4. - S. 41-45.

4. Ognev A. V. Spintronics: physical principle, structure, perspective / A. V. Ognev, A. S. Samardak // Vestnik DVO RAN. - 2006. - No. 4. -S. 70-80.
5. Danilov Yu. A. Magnetic semiconductor nanostructures for spintronic devices / Yu. A. Danilov // Prilozhenie k journal "Vestnik RGRTU". - 2009. - No. 4. - S. 1-6.
6. Danilov Yu. A. Basic spintronic: ucheb . p osobie / Yu. A. Danilov, E. S. Demidov, A. A. Ezhevsky. - Nizhny Novgorod, 2009. - 173 p.
7. Giant magnetoresistance of (001) Fe / (001)Cr magnetic superlattices / MN Baibich, JM Broto, A. Fert et al. // Phys. rev. Lett. - 1988. - Vol. 61, No. 21. -P. 2472-2475.
8. Binasch G. Enhanced magnetoresistance in layered magnetic structures with antiferromagnetic interlayer exchange / G. Binasch, P. Grunberg, F. Saurenbach // Phys. rev. B. - Vol. 39, No. 7. - P. 4828-4830.
9. Camley RE Theory of giant magnetoresistance effects in magnetic layered structures with antiferromagnetic coupling / RE Camley, J. Barnas // Phys. rev. Lett . -1989. - Vol. 63. - P. 664-667.